

A workshop report for the

International Workshop to Advance Ocean Carbon and Acidification Data Management and Interoperability

Venice, Italy, May 7-8, 2024

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report pertains to the International Workshop to Advance Ocean Carbon and Acidification Data Management and Interoperability that took place in Venice Italy on May 7 to 8, 2024. This Workshop brought together data managers from data assembly centers (DACs¹) and their stakeholders, including representatives of the global ocean carbon and acidification (OCA) research and observation community, representatives of international ocean data and information organizations, the European Marine Observation and Data Network, and custodians of relevant Sustainable Development Goal indicators. The primary goal of the workshop was to enable the research and observation community, the data management community, and end users of ocean carbon and acidification data to understand each other's needs, and discuss how to build on existing systems and infrastructures in order to optimize data flows and meet these needs. As part of this process, we worked towards reaching consensus on the use of metadata templates, controlled vocabularies, and data standards.

During the workshop, we identified some key requirements:

- Scientists shall only have to submit their data once: the repositories which receive submissions ***must interoperate with others*** to allow automated (meta)data sharing where appropriate.
- All ocean carbon and acidification data shall be published in a long-term archive with version control capabilities, and equipped with stable data citations linked to permanent, well-maintained, dereferenceable, and Web-accessible identifiers (e.g. W3IDs, DOIs).
- Ocean carbon and acidification (meta)data - regardless of where it is hosted - shall be discoverable and accessible. They shall be managed according to prevailing, international guidance on the effective implementation of the FAIR data principles and accessible to multiple types of end users with a minimum set of essential metadata.
- Metadata and data shall be formatted/serialized, marked up, and documented using open and broadly adopted formats, semantics and controlled vocabularies, regardless of which DAC they use.
- The (meta)data shall be fully traceable back to the complete set of source data and metadata referenceable through persistent, globally unique identifiers on the Web.

We agreed to work towards establishing a global network of distributed DACs, aligned through their use of common or compatible (meta)data formats, (meta)data standards and controlled vocabularies to enable the (meta)data to be globally findable and accessible, allowing one or multiple systems to easily access, work with, and serve them - in their totality - to their user communities as appropriate. Workshop participants aimed to have a minimum set of demonstrable examples assembled by the end of the year while workshop participants agreed on follow-on actions related to metadata, vocabularies, workflows, and federated (meta)data view².

¹ In this report, the concept of "Data Assembly Centre" also includes National Oceanography Data Centres involved in Ocean Carbon and Acidification data management

² Federated (meta)data is (meta)data that is hosted by multiple, independent digital systems, but is accessed and managed as a single, unified database.

SUMMARY NOTES

Workshop Goals

The overall goal of this workshop is to develop strategic guidance for international ocean carbon and acidification data management efforts and to pave a clear path forward for the next decade. Specifically, this workshop provided an opportunity to enable:

- (a) The data needs of the research community to be communicated to the data management community.
- (b) The creation of a global network of data assembly centers (DACs) to make sure that:
 - (i) Scientists only need to submit their data once.
 - (ii) Metadata and data will be documented using common templates and controlled vocabularies, regardless of which DAC they use.
 - (iii) Ocean carbon and acidification data can be findable and accessible through a unified data portal and services.
- (c) The representatives of individual DACs to get together to talk about metadata and data interoperability:
 - (i) Common metadata templates,
 - (ii) Controlled vocabularies,
 - (iii) Data standards.
- (d) Other requirements to be considered, including:
 - (i) Long-term archiving to ensure the data will be preserved on a long-term basis.
 - (ii) Version control capabilities to ensure each version of the data will be preserved on a perpetual basis.
 - (iii) Data citations linked to permanent, unique, and dereferenceable identifiers on the Web (e.g. DOIs).

Data Needs of the research community

The three scientific community priorities are: (a) Scientists only need to submit their data once, (b) They should be able to prepare metadata and data using common templates and controlled vocabularies, regardless of the DAC they choose to use, (c) the same (meta)data - regardless of where it is hosted should be findable and accessible through multiple data systems interoperating through shared norms and standards.

Additionally, the Workshop participants emphasized the importance of:

1. Streamlining data submissions. Data submission should be made as simple as possible, by:
 - a. Clearly identifying minimal, essential metadata to allow lower-effort submissions, while encouraging richer metadata submission in extended fields/interfaces.
 - b. Creating tailored data and metadata templates for a specific type of data like e.g. discrete-bottle based data, in-situ sensor data, laboratory experiment data, model output data.
 - c. Creating data submission interfaces that enable a user to pre-populate the metadata fields by inputting a DOI or other unique identifiers.
 - d. Adopting machine-readable cruise summary reports and/or Natural Language Processing methods to help with automated transmission and simple processing of common metadata elements.
2. Qualifying all data with rich and structured metadata to facilitate discovery, provenance tracking, QC efforts, and (re)use.
3. Each (meta)dataset's citation is linked to a permanent, dereferenceable, and unique identifier on the Web (e.g. a DOI, a W3ID).
4. Avoiding non-functional and/or unintentional redundancy (e.g. outside of agreed content mirroring, brokerage, or backup), particularly when leading to broken or splintered provenance and version tracking.
5. Consistent data flow with the QC community is desirable. No consensus was reached during this Workshop.

A global Network of DACs

The workshop participants unanimously recognized the importance of establishing a global network of DACs to meet the data needs of the ocean carbon and acidification research communities. Such DACs must adopt community-driven metadata templates that share foundational community agreed-on metadata attributes, controlled vocabularies, and data standards, and make their data discoverable and accessible through a unified data access portal and data services. Additionally, the data should be safeguarded in long-term archive(s) with version control capabilities, with data citations linked to digital object identifiers (DOIs).

Regional DACs that meet the specified criteria can serve the data needs of one or more countries in the region. Scientists not required to submit data to their own NODCs are welcome to submit their data to any of the regional DACs. Each participating DAC would make their machine-readable metadata, aligned to controlled vocabularies, available to a unified data access interface, so as to enable their data holdings to be searchable through the one-stop interface. After the dataset is located, a user can then be taken to the metadata and data downloading

interfaces of the respective DAC. The Global Ocean Acidification Observing Network (GOA-ON) Data Explorer (<http://portal.goa-on.org/Explorer>) was presented as a potential candidate for this one-stop data access portal thanks to its user-friendly interface that features clickable maps. Data discovery services presented by ODIS is another solution to be considered. The plan is to create a search interface and display search results on a map, allowing users to click on ship tracks or other icons to access the data.

Metadata templates

Community driven metadata templates and controlled vocabularies that will be adopted by all participating DACs will be the key to a successful global network as described above. Scientists emphasized the importance of having easy-to-fill-out metadata templates because long metadata lists hinder data submissions as they pose additional demands on their time. On the other hand, it is critical to document all necessary metadata elements for future data use, including quality control. A good compromise is to: (a) create data type specific metadata templates, allowing users to only enter metadata elements related to the specific type of data; (b) enable users to prepopulate all metadata elements based on previously published datasets of similar type, and modify them from there instead of starting from scratch; and (c) automatically generate some metadata elements, such as the bounding box longitude and latitude, start date, end date, and minimum and maximum sampling depths.

Despite the importance of data type specific metadata templates, it will be critical to establish an overall framework that can accommodate all metadata elements of all data types. Such a metadata template was the focus of this Workshop. The participants examined and commented on a metadata template that was an aggregation of the following metadata templates: the Ocean Carbon and Acidification Data System (OCADS, Jiang et al., 2023a) metadata template (Jiang et al., 2015), the SDG 14.3.1 metadata template (a slightly modified OCADS metadata template), the Surface Ocean CO₂ Atlas (SOCAT), and the EMODnet metadata template based on SeaDataNet standards. As a long term strategy, each community should aim to collect all metadata elements included in the consolidated template and ensure appropriate mapping.

Useful links:

The updated metadata template is available [here](#).

Controlled vocabularies

Controlled vocabularies are lists of pre-defined and standardized terms against which metadata entries are mapped. By using a limited and standardized set of terms, controlled vocabularies help improve metadata interpretation, data findability and interoperability by eliminating spelling variations, synonyms, and other forms of variability. In order to make ocean carbon and acidification data interoperable with other domains, any agreed metadata template and standard must use controlled vocabularies to uniquely, consistently and unambiguously identify metadata values for certain elements such as e.g. observed properties, observation types, instruments, and platform types.

There was a general consensus on the importance of using controlled vocabularies that are managed in semantic repositories like the NERC Vocabulary Server to guarantee long-term accessibility by both humans and software, and to enable the creation of mappings between terminologies. Connection between systems and machine-actionability requires persistent and reliable access to controlled vocabularies through unambiguous, persistent and unique identifiers (URIs) managed in semantic repositories that are aligned with web technology standards and best practices. However, during the workshop, we were unable to agree on which controlled vocabularies to adopt moving forward, especially for variables. The following requirements and observations were established during the workshop:

- Adopted templates and common data formats and metadata fields need to be constrained by controlled vocabularies served from a trusted vocabulary server using web standards and identifiers (URIs);
- The adoption of common vocabularies for data exchange and metadata harmonization could be implemented on top of existing practices at individual DACs; i.e. either the DAC adopts the agreed common vocabularies or the DAC maintains a crosswalk between their vocabularies and the one chosen for data exchange;
- For platform types and instances, for instrument types and models, and for units, existing vocabularies were clearly aligned with the Ocean Carbon and Acidification data community requirements and plans could therefore be made to extend and adopt them;
- For variable names more discussion was needed but a number of key requirements and statement of fact were established:
 - The vocabulary(ies) adopted need to comply with the FAIR data principles and in particular enable cross-domain interoperability;
 - It needs to enable machine-access (i.e. compliant with web standards) as well as human readability;
 - If more than one vocabulary is used for the same concept then they will need to be mapped and the mapping will need to be maintained;
 - There already exists many variable-naming vocabularies and we need to avoid creating new ones unless necessary;
 - Most variables needed by the OCA community, including e.g. Temperature of pH measurement, already have a vocabulary code in either the CF Standard Names or the BODC PUV;
 - Existing vocabularies should be reviewed by experts to ensure they are correct, and superfluous or ambiguous ones can be deprecated;
 - Large standardized vocabularies like the CF Standard Names or the BODC PUV are difficult to use because they cover multiple domains and provide detailed information to avoid ambiguity but they can be subset to only show the variables that are relevant to the OCA community;
 - Large controlled vocabularies like CF Standard Names or the BODC PUV are not always fit for providing human-readable column headers: in order to achieve this for the OCA community, they can be combined with a set of concise labels to be used in field names and column headers of templates and data files.

The points made during the workshop and highlighted above will be used to propose a solution as a way forward, including the possibility of creating machine-readable mappings between

various vocabularies. A group will meet again before the end of the year to detail the various options, including their pros-and-cons.

Useful links:

- (a) [The NERC Vocabulary Server \(NVS, BODC/SeaDataNet\)](#)
- (b) [Climate and Forecast \(CF\) Standard Names](#)
- (c) [NASA GCMD Keywords](#)
- (d) [Vocabularies](#) developed by [Jiang et al. \(2023b\)](#) out of the mCDR data management discussions.
- (e) Table 1 of [Jiang et al. \(2015\)](#) also lists some controlled vocabularies for observed properties.

Data standards

Data standards are sets of rules and specifications to define how data should be stored, structured, and formatted. They help facilitate data exchange and interpretation, and promote interoperability and consistency. In the management of oceanographic data, data standards cover elements such as the technical format for storing data (e.g., Microsoft Excel, Comma Separated Values or CSV, NetCDF); standardized column headers or abbreviations; units; standardized methods for calculating certain variables; standardized quality control flagging schemes; missing value indicators; etc.

Two types of data standards were presented at the Workshop: DAC-specific machine-readable data standards, and research community-driven user-friendly standards. Workshop participants think it is critical to provide data standards that are user friendly and produced using bottom up approaches by working closely with the research community. Such standards should be independent of any DAC requirements. Additionally, it is preferable to create data standards that are machine readable.

The participants also talked about:

- (a) Whether the metadata information above the column headers should be stored in a separate worksheet, because they are often deleted before loading the data into QC programs
- (b) Whether the QC flag conventions, e.g., 2 - good, 3 - questionable, 4 - bad, 6 - median of duplicates, and 9 - missing, should be added as part of the required metadata information within the data, or the flagging scheme reference should be added to metadata.
- (c) Whether a link to the definition of the column header abbreviations, e.g., <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/ocean-carbon-acidification-data-system/support/profile.html>, should be added to the metadata information within the data.

Useful references from the meeting:

EMODnet data standards:

Dataset format adopted by EMODnet Chemistry, following SeaDataNet standards are described here: <https://www.seadatanet.org/Standards/Data-Transport-Formats>

Each dataset is associated with a set of metadata used for data discovery in the Common Data Index (CDI): <https://www.seadatanet.org/Standards/Metadata-formats/CDI>

Methodological and quality control/quality assurance information is collected using a questionnaire that can be linked to the CDI: <https://zenodo.org/records/11109103>

Data standards hosted at NCEI/OCADS:

- (a) Profile Data: Discrete bottle samples
 - [Column Header Names Description](#)
 - [Data File \(.XLSX\) Example](#)
- (b) Underway Data
 - [Column Header Names Description](#)
 - [Data File \(.XLSX\) Example](#)
- (c) Autonomous Sensor Data: Mooring, Saildrone, Argo, glider, etc.
 - [Column Header Names Description](#)
 - [Data File \(.XLSX\) Example](#)
- (d) Physiological Response Data: Laboratory experiment, Mesocosm, Field experiment, Natural analogue, etc.
 - [Column Header Names Description](#)
 - [Data File \(.XLSX\) Example](#)

Data Licensing

Participants were in agreements that any license model should be open and not prohibit the use of data. Different license texts and schemes are adopted by national institutions (e.g NOAA adopts CC0-1) and these should be respected.

The desire to track data usage is constrained by national policies. There was agreement that the most reliable mechanism to track data use and citation is that provided by DOIs.

Data Workflow

Data workflows are foundational to accomplish other objectives listed above - submit once, ensure data are delivered for synthesis products. Data workflows address the procession of data from submission, availability, and archive location, and identifies those entities responsible.

Attendees discussed the contrast of submitting data to synthesis product teams (SOCAT, GLODAP) vs a DAC. It was made clear that data should not be submitted to GLODAP. SOCAT is a data submission point. EMODnet acts as a DAC for European countries. Data could be submitted to a DAC and then routed to synthesis products where specific metadata and QC objectives would be addressed. The advantages and disadvantages of this approach were considered. As these workflows are considered at follow-up meetings it was emphasized that planning should be forward looking (for the next decade) and not short term. The reality of data submission and required workflows demanded by national policies will also dictate how data are routed. No definitive decision was reached and this topic will be the focus of a dedicated follow-on workshop.

Follow-on actions

Areas of broad consensus were reached and attendees agreed to pursue further discussion and development as tactically focussed follow-on workshop sessions. The IOC offered venues for a follow-on workshop and the coordination of the groups tasked with the actions listed below. Other opportunities are a meeting before AGU 2024 2024 fall meeting or the interim OceanObs meeting in 2025. Follow-on meeting will address one or more of the actions listed below, and is intended to be more tactical to focus on implementation and funding.

The action and task leads were identified:

- Vocabularies
 - Leads: Gwenaëlle Moncoiffé, support from Pier Luigi Buttigieg, Steve Jones
 - Tasks: CF, non-parameter related vocabularies, parameter naming vocabularies, header mapping
- Metadata
 - Leads: Liqing Jiang, Chris Sabine, Alessandra Giorgetti, Pier Luigi Buttigieg, Steve Jones, Gwenaëlle Moncoiffé
 - Wrap up loose ends
- federated data view (data discovery)
 - Leads: Troy Tanner, Pier Luigi Buttigieg, Kevin O'Brien
 - Tasks: Data discovery across regional data holdings, DACs
- QC integration
 - Leads: Michele Giani , Steve Jones, Chris Sabine
 - Tasks: Determine QC integration into the data lifecycle, determine the levels of QC
- Workflows
 - Leads: Eugene Burger, Kevin O'Brien, Pier-Luigi Buttigieg
 - Tasks: Determine a vision for data workflows that integrates across DACs/NODCs, develop the next steps to “on-stop” data submission

Appendix I. STEERING COMMITTEE MEMBERS

- Alessandra Giorgetti (OGS, Italy)
- Alex Kozyr (UMD and NCEI, USA)
- Elisabeth Kubin (OGS, Italy)
- Eugene Burger (PMEL, USA)
- Gwenaelle Moncoiffé (BODC, UK)
- Katherina Schoo (IOC and GOA-ON, France)
- Li-Qing Jiang (UMD and NCEI, USA)
- Marina Lipizer (OGS, Italy)

Appendix II. WORKSHOP ATTENDEES

Name	Affiliation	In person or remote
Alessandra Giorgetti	Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS, Italy	In person
Alex Kozyr	NOAA/National Centers for Environmental Information; University of Maryland, USA	In person
Alyse A. Larkin	NOAA Global Ocean Monitoring and Observing (GOMO), USA	Remote
Bronte Tilbrook	Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO), Australia	Remote
Carolina Berys-Gonzalez	CLIVAR and Carbon Hydrographic Data Office (CCHDO), USA	In person
Christopher L. Sabine	University of Hawaii at Manoa, USA	In person
Elisabeth Kubin	Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS, Italy	In person
Eugene F. Burger	NOAA Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory (PMEL), USA	In person
Evin McGovern	Marine Institute, Ireland	Remote
Gwenaelle Moncoiffe	National Oceanography Centre - British Oceanographic Data Centre, UK	In person
Ivona Cetinic	NASA Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC), USA	Remote
Janet Ann Newton	University of Washington, USA	In person
Kaity A. Goldsmith	NOAA Ocean Acidification Program, USA	In person
Katherina L. Schoo	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO, France	In person
Kathy Tedesco	NOAA Global Ocean Monitoring and Observing (GOMO), USA	Remote
Kevin Michael O'Brien	University of Washington; NOAA Pacific Marine Environmental laboratory (PMEL), USA	In person
Kirsten Isensee	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO, France	Remote
Kyla J. Kelly	NOAA Global Ocean Monitoring and Observing (GOMO), USA	In person
Li Xiao	National marine data and Information Service, China	Remote
Li-Qing Jiang	NOAA/National Centers for Environmental Information; University of Maryland, USA	In person
Lu Wenhai	National Marine Data and Information Service, China	In person
Marina Lipizer	Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS, Italy	In person
Megan Anne French	Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS, Italy	In person
Michele Giani	Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS, Italy	In person
Nico Lange	NORCE Norwegian Research Centre, Norway	In person

Pier Luigi Buttigieg	Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz centre for polar and marine research, Germany	In person
Richard A. Feely	NOAA Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory (PMEL), USA	Remote
RikWanninkhof	NOAA Atlantic Oceanic and Meteorological Laboratory (AOML), USA	Remote
Siv K Lauvset	NORCE Norwegian Research Centre, Norway	Remote
Steve Jones	University of Bergen, Norway	In person
Troy Tanner	University of Washington, USA	In person

Appendix III. MEETING AGENDA, PRESENTATION FILES AND MEETING NOTES

Tuesday, May 7, 2024

Time	Activities
8:00	Arriving and picking up name tags
8:10	Welcome and introductions (20 min) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome and logistics - Elisabeth Kubin (10 min) • Workshop goals - Li-Qing Jiang (5 min) • Building towards common data management objectives - Eugene Burger (5 min)
8:30	Data management and infrastructure needs from the research community (90 min) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentations by science colleagues - Bronte, Chris, Dick, Rik (5 min) • GLODAP – Siv Lauvset and Nico Lange (10 min) • SOCAT – Dorothee Bakker and Kevin O'Brien (10 min) • EMODnet Chemistry - Alessandra Giorgetti (10 min) • Data management needs of the UN SDG 14.3.1 indicator – Katherina Schoo (10 min) • Discussion (Lead: Kevin O'Brien): other data requirements or preferences from the research community (50 min) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data sharing between NODCs and synthesis products • DOIs for each NODCs (Dorothee) • Plans and possible solutions • Sustainability of the data management efforts
10:00	Coffee break (15 min)
10:15	An envisioned international data management network, composed of multiple DACs (105 min): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The SDG 14.3.1 led discussion outcome - Katherina Schoo and Kevin O'Brien (5 min) • The OARS discussion outcome from Lima, Peru - Jan Newton and Li-Qing Jiang (5 min) • Globally federating ocean carbon data flows with the Ocean Data and Information System - Pier Luigi Buttigieg (5 min) • What we can learn from the HELIOS - Chris Sabine (5 min) • Ocean Acidification data and metadata within the European marine data service EMODnet Chemistry - Elisabeth Kubin (5 min) • OCADS - Li-Qing and Alex (5 min) • Discussion (Lead: Elisabeth Kubin) (70 min)
12:00	Lunch break (90 min)
13:30	Metadata template (120 min) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working from existing efforts to harmonize metadata elements and interchange formats, finalize a metadata framework that can be applied to all major types of ocean carbon and acidification data - Liqing Jiang (5 min) • Discussion (Lead: Chris Sabine) (115 min): Current metadata structure and elements that can best serve the needs of international ocean carbon and acidification data management, required elements and 'good to have'.
15:30	Coffee break (15 min)

15:40 - 17:30	Controlled vocabularies (120 min) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Controlled vocabularies – presented by Gwen Moncoiffé (10 min) • Discussion (Lead: Gwen Moncoiffé) (110 min): vocabularies that should be adopted by all DACs.
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Wednesday, May 8, 2024

Time	Activities
8:30	Data standards (90 min) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing data standards: file format, column header, QC flag, etc. - Li-Qing Jiang (5 min) • Discussion (Lead: Steve Jones): identifying and adopting data standards for ocean carbon and acidification research. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How data should be presented. Original format or machine readable format
10:00	Coffee break (15 min)
10:15	Other considerations (Lead: Katherina Schoo) (135 min) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data licensing • QC flagging scheme(s) to consider • Preferred pH scale • Reporting calculated vs measured variables • ICES ship code for uncrewed platforms
12:30	Lunch break
13:30	Workshop proceedings (90 min) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A manuscript to document this first international workshop on ocean carbon and acidification data management • Discussion (Lead: Chris Sabine)
15:00	Coffee break (15 min)
15:15	Other items (70 min) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-AGU follow-up meeting - Eugene, Li-Qing and others • Planning for the next Workshop • Discussion (Lead: Eugene Burger)
16:25	Meeting adjourn (the room must be cleared before 16:30 pm)

Appendix IV. DATA MANAGEMENT TERMINOLOGY

- **Data management** refers to the process of ingesting, preserving, and making data packages findable and accessible. Data management efforts often involve leveraging long-term archives, providing version control, organizing and storing metadata using community metadata templates and controlled vocabularies, adhering to data standards, and offering data citations with DOIs, etc. It ensures maximum use, value, and trust of data by present and future generations by establishing processes and policies that enable broad discovery, access, interoperability, and reusability. Data management is frequently mandated by international, national, and local regulations.
- **Data synthesis efforts** (e.g., SOCAT and GLODAP) refers to the process of quality controlling, and consolidation of information from diverse sources into a cohesive and structured format. Their outcomes often involve the development of data products (e.g., cruise data compilations, gridded climatologies, etc.) for the purpose of providing additional value to users. Like other research activities, data collation efforts also need data management support to preserve the original disparate data packages as well as the developed data products.
- **Data assembly centers (DAC)** is a facility or organization that ingests, documents, and distributes data from various sources. These centers play a crucial role in consolidating disparate data packages collected from different laboratories, documenting their metadata, applying controlled vocabularies, and making them findable and accessible to users.
- **Long term archives** refer to specialized repositories or storage systems designed to preserve digital information over extended periods of time, often spanning decades or even centuries. The paramount objective of a long term archive is to safeguard the integrity and accessibility of digital assets for future generations. This typically involves storing multiple copies of a data package across both online servers and offline tapes, encompassing both on-premise and off-site locations, to ensure the data will be safe against human errors, hacking, and natural disasters.
- **Metadata** refers to a group of structured information that describes an information resource, e.g., an oceanographic data package, enabling its findability, accessibility, and usability. For oceanographic data, a metadata record could document such information as what was measured; by whom; when (temporal coverage); where (geographic coverage); how was it sampled and analyzed; with what instruments and following what protocol; and what were its units of measure and quality of the data. Metadata is also commonly called data about data.
- **Data Dictionaries** describe the context, and the description of the metadata.

Data dictionaries trend to the IT side of data management, and may contain the definition of the metadata element composition (numeric, alpa-numeric, number of characters etc.)

- **Controlled vocabularies** are defined as lists of pre-defined and standardized terms. The use of controlled vocabularies plays a very important role in effective data management, as it helps ensure that the data are documented, findable, and accessible in a consistent way. By using a limited and standardized set of terms, controlled vocabularies help improve metadata interpretation and data findability by eliminating spelling variations, synonyms, and other forms of variability. Additionally, controlled vocabularies help facilitate metadata interoperability between different systems, making it easier to exchange and integrate data between different organizations and platforms.
- **Data portals:** A data portal is a web-based platform or application that enables a user to search for and access various datasets.
- **Data tools:** e.g., ERDDAP is a tool that can be of great utility to make data machine-readable, and accessible in various formats, enabling users to access a subset of a large data product.

Appendix V. PUBLICATION LIST RELATED TO OCEAN CARBON AND ACIDIFICATION DATA MANAGEMENT

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Jiang, L.-Q., Arzayus, K. M., Gattuso, J.-P., Chandler, C., Garcia, H. E., Kozyr, A., Yang, Y., Thomas, R., Beck, B., Spears, T. (2016). How to document ocean acidification data, *Limnology and Oceanography e-Lectures*, <https://doi.org/10.1002/loe2.10004>.

Jiang L.-Q., Pierrot, D., Wanninkhof, R., Feely, R. A., Tilbrook, B., Alin, S., et al. (2022). Best practice data standards for discrete chemical oceanographic observations.

Frontiers in Marine Science, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.705638>.

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<https://doi.org/10.5194/sp-2-oae2023-13-2023>.

Riebesell, U., Fabry, V. J., Hansson, L., & Gattuso, J. P. (2011). Guide to best practices for ocean acidification research and data reporting. Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, <https://doi.org/10.2777/66906>.

Sutton, A. J., Battisti, R., Carter, B., Evans, W., Newton, J., Alin, S., et al. (2022). Advancing best practices for assessing trends of ocean acidification time series.

Frontiers in Marine Science, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.1045667>.

Tanhua, T., Pouliquen, S., Hausman, J., O'Brien, K., Bricher, P., de Bruin, T., et al. (2019). Ocean Fair Data Services. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00440>.

Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

Appendix VI. MEETING NOTES

Detailed meeting notes are available in [this pdf file](#).

Appendix VII. DAC SURVEY RESULTS

Survey results for the existing Data Assembly Centers are available [here](#).